

Mechanisms of Laser Ablation in Liquids and Their Impact on the Efficiency of Nanoparticle Generation

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Abstract:

Laser ablation in liquid is a versatile and environmentally friendly method for producing nanoparticles from a wide range of materials. While recent advances have significantly increased productivity, laser ablation in liquid remains less energy-efficient than ablation in air. Simulations have suggested that this discrepancy arises from redeposition of ablated material, but experimental validation has so far been lacking. Here, we quantify the energy efficiency of laser ablation in liquid and provide direct experimental verification of redeposition. An absorption-corrected one-to-one comparison of single-pulse ablation in air and water shows that the absorption-corrected specific energy for ablation increases fourfold in water due to redeposition, from 50 J mm^{-3} to 200 J mm^{-3} . For multi-pulse conditions, the required energy for ablation based on the incident pulse energy amounts to 431 J mm^{-3} , corresponding to an order-of-magnitude improvement compared to the best ultrafast LAL value of 3333 J mm^{-3} reported to date. These findings establish the practical potential of LAL for green and energy-efficient nanoparticle synthesis.

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1. Introduction

Laser ablation in liquid (LAL), first introduced by Fojtik and Henglein,^[1,2] is now a mature technique for nanoparticle generation from virtually any material.^[3–6] Unlike chemical nanoparticle synthesis routes, LAL produces surfactant-free nanoparticles^[7] and adheres to green chemistry principles.^[8] Additionally, the nanoparticles are defect-rich^[7,9,10] due to rapid cooling rates of 1 K ps^{-1} to 10 K ps^{-1} .^[11] These properties make them attractive for catalysis,^[12] with demonstrated applications in hydrogen generation,^[9] energy conversion,^[10] water remediation,^[13] and automotive exhaust gas treatment.^[14] Yet, compared to laser ablation in air, LAL exhibits up to an order of magnitude lower ablation efficiency,^[11,15,16] which remains a major restriction for industrial adoption.^[6,17]

In LAL, the laser pulse must first propagate through the liquid, where at intensities exceeding $10^{12} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ multiphoton absorption and cascade ionization cause optical breakdown by raising the free-carrier density above the critical value of $\approx 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.^[18] As a result, up to 80% of the laser pulse energy can be absorbed in the liquid.^[19] At the metal surface, the laser energy is deposited into conduction band electrons^[20–23] and transferred to the lattice within the electron-phonon coupling time ($\approx 1 \text{ ps}$ for stainless steel^[24] and $\approx 20 \text{ ps}$ for Au^[25]) as described by the two-temperature model.^[26]

For peak fluences below approximately three times the ablation threshold,^[27,28] spallation is initiated if the stress confinement condition is fulfilled.^[27,29] In this case, isochoric heating generates compressive stress waves with amplitudes of several GPa, which are back-reflected at the free surface as tensile waves.^[27,30–32] If the tensile wave pressure exceeds the spall strength, a molten layer is released.^[33] At peak fluences exceeding approximately three times the ablation threshold,^[27,28] phase explosion occurs as the lattice temperature approaches the critical point.^[34] This results in disintegration of the overheated surface into droplets, clusters, and atoms.^[27,32,35]

In air, the ablated material expands freely after approximately 10 ps,^[27,36] reaching velocities from hundreds of m s^{-1} for spallation^[37] to several km s^{-1} for phase explosion.^[38] In liquid, the expanding material is rapidly decelerated and confined by the inertia of the surrounding liquid^[39–42] to a height of tens to hundreds of nanometers within approximately 100 ps.^[43,44] Simulations predict that this can lead to partial or full redeposition of the ablated material back onto the surface, thereby reducing efficiency compared to ablation in air.^[11,43,44] Upon deceleration of the ablated material, nanoparticles form either by condensation of atoms and

clusters or through fragmentation of the spallation layer by thermodynamic instabilities within the first nanoseconds,^[44–46] resulting in a bimodal size distribution.^[47–52]

The hot ablated material also initiates the formation of a cavitation bubble through rapid vaporization of the liquid,^[44] with the preceding shockwave facilitating this process by locally dropping the pressure below the vaporization threshold.^[53] Cavitation bubble expansion begins approximately 1 ns after pulse impact^[16,54] and proceeds on the nanosecond to microsecond timescale, reaching its maximum diameter after a few microseconds.^[54,55] After cavitation bubble collapse, secondary redeposition of nanoparticles onto the target may occur, while other nanoparticles are released into the surrounding liquid.^[56–59] Following the collapse, persistent microbubbles may remain in the liquid for tens of milliseconds.^[60] The cavitation bubble, persistent microbubbles, and suspended nanoparticles shield subsequent pulses and thereby reduce ablation efficiency and hence productivity.^[61,62]

To overcome these efficiency losses, various strategies have been employed: cavitation bubble shielding has been mitigated through fast scanning techniques^[63] and multi-beam processing,^[64] extinction by nanoparticles and microbubbles reduced using liquid-flow reactors^[65] or wire-target ablation in liquid jets,^[66] and nonlinear absorption avoided through spatio-temporal focusing.^[67] This has advanced LAL productivity into the grams-per-hour range,^[63,68,69] positioning it as a competitive alternative to chemical nanoparticle synthesis routes.^[17,70]

However, these strategies do not address the confinement-induced redeposition of ablated material,^[11,43,44] a mechanism that simulations predict to reduce ablation efficiency by up to 80%.^[11] Yet, this mechanism has not yet been experimentally verified or quantified. The present work addresses this gap by providing direct experimental verification of redeposition and quantifying the amount of redeposited material.

To this end, we performed a rigorous one-to-one comparison of laser ablation in air and water under identical absorbed fluences, quantified by measuring linear and nonlinear transmission losses in water, as well as self-reflectance. To unambiguously isolate the effect of redeposition, experiments were performed using single pulses, thereby eliminating shielding by cavitation bubbles, nanoparticles, and persistent microbubbles, as well as multi-pulse incubation effects.^[71–73] Furthermore, complementary multi-pulse experiments were performed to assess the achievable LAL efficiency under conditions where shielding by nanoparticles is present, resembling scalability-oriented liquid-flow reactors in which bubble shielding is suppressed.^[61,63]

Two representative materials were selected: Au, with weak electron-phonon coupling and high thermal conductivity,^[74] and Fe_{0.5}Ni_{0.5} (hereafter denoted as FeNi), with strong coupling and low conductivity,^[75] providing contrasting thermophysical properties and direct comparability to prior simulation results.

Pump-probe microscopy (PPM), which enables the identification of ablation mechanisms such as spallation or phase explosion by measuring the transient reflectance change, was employed.^[37,76–78] For Au, measurements exist comparing ablation in air and water, but the height of the ablated material cannot be reliably extracted.^[54] In contrast, FeNi exhibits clear spallation features in air and Newton rings can be used to quantitatively resolve the height of the ablated layer,^[77] allowing direct identification of confinement and redeposition by comparing the ablated material height between air and water.

This experimental design enables us to verify redeposition and quantify the amount of material redeposited. It also demonstrates the potential for further increasing the efficiency of LAL.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Suppression of ablation efficiency in water revealed by single-pulse experiments

Figure 1 shows the single-pulse absorption-corrected ablation efficiency and ablation morphology for Au and FeNi. Because longer pulses interact with the ablated material,^[79,80] it is essential to ensure that absorption is measured at the target surface. This requires the pulse to be absorbed within the acoustic relaxation time τ_{ac} (≈ 50 ps for Au^[54] and ≈ 5 ps for FeNi^[75]). Furthermore, nonlinear absorption prevents single-pulse ablation in water at 500 fs;^[67] therefore, a pulse duration of 3 ps was chosen.

At an absorbed peak fluence of 0.5 J cm^{-2} , ablation of Au in air yields a smoother and narrower crater than in water (Figure 1a). The maximum ablation efficiency reaches $20 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in air but only $5 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in water at 1 J cm^{-2} (Figure 1b). In air, this corresponds to specific energy for ablation of 50 J mm^{-3} , which is close to the vaporization energy density of 42 J mm^{-3} (Supporting Information, Section S1), whereas in water 200 J mm^{-3} are required, exceeding the vaporization energy density by a factor of about five. In water, the ablation threshold fluence is increased by about 50% (Supporting Information, Section S2), and ablation sets in only in the phase explosion regime (Figure 1b), with the phase explosion threshold determined by two-temperature-model simulations (Supporting Information, Section S3).

For FeNi at 0.5 J cm^{-2} , ablation in air produces a crater with sharp edges, whereas in water only randomly distributed resolidified spots are visible (Figure 1c). In air, the ablation efficiency reaches $5 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$, while in water no ablation is detected (Figure 1d). The efficiency in air corresponds to 200 J mm^{-3} , about three times higher than the equilibrium vaporization energy density of 70 J mm^{-3} (Supporting Information, Section S1). The higher factor compared to Au can be explained by the higher tensile strength of FeNi ($800 \text{ MPa}^{[81]}$ versus $100 \text{ MPa}^{[82]}$ for Au).^[75] In water the ablation threshold is increased by about 300% (Supporting Information, Section S2) and ablation sets in far within the phase explosion regime (Figure 1d). In this regime, a porous crater forms (Figure 1e) and the ablation efficiency fluctuates around zero with an average of $-0.4 \text{ } \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$. Negative ablation volumes and efficiencies are measured because the porous rim volume exceeds that of the crater center. This likely results from oxygen generation and subsequent oxidation at the crater rim, since Fe and Ni have high redox potentials and form lower-density oxides,^[83,84] and may be further enhanced by subsurface voids that are unresolved by confocal microscopy.^[85]

Figure 1. Ablation morphology and absorption-corrected volumetric ablation efficiency η_{abs} in air and water for Au and FeNi irradiated with a single $\tau_p = 3 \text{ ps}$ laser pulse with a beam waist radius of $w_0 = 15 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$. **a** SEM images of craters formed by irradiating Au with an absorbed peak fluence of $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 0.5 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$ in air (left, red frame) and water (right, blue frame). **b** η_{abs} versus Φ_{abs} for ablation of Au in air (red squares) and water (blue circles). The axis on

the right shows the absorption-corrected specific energy for ablation ζ_{abs} . The phase explosion threshold fluence Φ_{PE} , obtained from two-temperature model calculations is indicated by a dashed vertical line. **c** Same as **a**, but for FeNi. **d** Same as **b**, but for FeNi. **e** SEM image of FeNi irradiated in water at $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 3.0 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$. Note that the η_{abs} axis ranges differ between panels **b** and **d**.

Figures 1b and 1d demonstrate that ablation is observed in air but fully suppressed in water in the spallation regime. Since transmission losses as well as shielding by cavitation bubbles, persistent microbubbles, and nanoparticles can be excluded, the suppression must have another origin.

A possible explanation may be a change in acoustic reflectance, which determines the fraction of the compressive wave converted into the tensile wave driving spallation.^[29] In air, it is 99.9%, whereas in water it decreases to 92.7% for Au and 93.7% for FeNi (Supporting Information, Section S4), reducing the tensile stress by about 7%. Since pressure scales linearly with absorbed energy density,^[29,86] this effect would raise the threshold by only 7%, well below the observed 50% for Au and 300% for FeNi (Supporting Information, Section S2).

Moreover, thermal conduction from the target into water is negligible. Even for nanosecond pulses, only about 4% of the absorbed energy is transferred to the liquid.^[87] This value represents an upper limit, as ablation with picosecond pulses exhibits even lower thermal losses.^[88] Thermal conduction can therefore be excluded as the cause of the increased ablation threshold and reduced efficiency in water.

With acoustic reflectance and thermal conduction losses excluded, redeposition of ablated material remains as a possible origin of the reduced ablation efficiency in water.

2.2. Verification of spallation-layer redeposition in water using pump-probe microscopy

To verify the occurrence of redeposition in the spallation regime, PPM was used to investigate the ablation dynamics of FeNi at an absorbed peak fluence of 0.13 J cm^{-2} , at which point spallation in air is expected, while spallation in water is completely suppressed (Figure 1d).

Figure 2 shows the relative reflectance change measured by PPM during the first nanosecond after excitation; the complete transient up to $10 \mu\text{s}$ is provided in Section S5 of the Supporting Information. In air, outward-curved reflectance oscillations are observed between 50 ps and 1 ns, consistent with the release of a spallation layer whose propagation velocity scales with the local fluence, being higher at the beam center than at the edges (Figure 2a,

top).^[28,37,77,89,90] These Newton rings arise from interference between reflections at the propagating spallation layer and the underlying surface.^[28,37,77,89,90] Fitting the transient using the transfer-matrix method (Supporting Information, Section S6) confirms that the reflectance change originates from a freely propagating spallation layer of ≈ 11 nm thickness expanding into air at a velocity of about 1500 m s⁻¹ (Figure 2c). At long delays ($\Delta t = 10$ s in Figure 2a), a sharp crater edge at $r \approx 12$ μ m and nearly zero reflectance change inside the crater ($r < 12$ μ m) are observed, consistent with the crater morphology shown in Figure 1c.

Figure 2. Comparison of ablation dynamics in air and water for FeNi irradiated with $\tau_p = 3$ ps and $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 0.13$ J cm⁻² (spallation regime). **a** Color-coded spatiotemporal relative reflectance change $\Delta R/R_0$ of FeNi in air (top) and water (bottom). The panel on the right represents the final state at 10 s. **b** $\Delta R/R_0$ at $r = 0$ μ m for ablation in air (red squares) and water (blue circles). The cyan and orange lines represent a fit of the reflectance using the transfer matrix method. **c** Spallation layer height h versus delay time obtained from transfer matrix calculations in air, and **d** in water. Note the strongly different height scales in **c** and **d**.

For ablation in water, only a weak negative relative reflectance change ($\Delta R/R_0 = -0.15$) is observed within the first 20 ps (Figure 2a, bottom, and Figure 2b). The initial reflectance decrease was analyzed using the transfer-matrix method, with all optical parameters and the spallation-layer thickness fixed to the values determined in the air case, while only the spallation-layer trajectory was varied (Supporting Information, Section S6). Under this constraint, the transient is reproduced if the spallation layer expands to ≈ 11 nm at 20 ps and redeposits at ≈ 60 ps (Figure 2d). Newton rings would only be expected for displacements

larger than 130 nm (one quarter of the 520 nm probe wavelength) and are therefore not observed in the signal. This result agrees reasonably well with molecular-dynamics simulations predicting maximum displacements of ≈ 40 nm under comparable conditions.^[11]

After ≈ 50 ps, oscillations with a period of ≈ 100 ps appear, showing a low maximum relative reflectance modulation of $\approx 5\%$. Using the refractive index of water at 520 nm ($n = 1.336$),^[91] this period corresponds to a propagation velocity of ≈ 2000 m s⁻¹, in close agreement with simulations predicting the same shockwave velocity in the spallation regime.^[11] The low fringe contrast further supports the interpretation of this oscillation as originating from a shockwave, which induces a refractive-index change on the order of $\Delta n \approx 10^{-3}$ and thus modulates reflectance by only a few percent.^[92]

The relative reflectance rises above zero after 200 ps and reaches ≈ 0.15 at 1 ns. An estimate shows that a 50 nm vapor-filled bubble^[11] above the FeNi surface would increase the reflectance from 0.53 (Supporting Information, Section S7) to 0.63, corresponding to $\Delta R/R_0 = 0.19$. This agreement indicates that the positive reflectance originates from cavitation-bubble formation, consistent with reports of bubble onset at ≈ 1 ns.^[16,54]

The time-resolved results therefore support that redeposition explains both the suppression of ablation efficiency in the spallation regime (Figure 1d) and the absence of a clear crater edge (Figure 1c).

2.3. Verification of redeposition in the phase explosion regime using pulse duration variation

This section focuses on the phase-explosion regime, using Au as the sample material. For Au, significant ablation in water is observed (Figure 1b), and the analysis now turns to the pulse-duration dependence.

Figure 3a shows the dependence of the absorption-corrected ablation efficiency on pulse duration for Au at $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 3$ J cm⁻², which lies well within the phase explosion regime (Figure 1b). In air, the efficiency decreases from $17 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ at 3 ps to $1.5 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ at 50 ps and vanishes at 90 ps, whereas in water it increases by $\approx 50\%$ from 3 ps to 10 ps and then remains nearly constant at $\approx 4 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$. As a result, the ablation efficiencies in air and water converge as the pulse duration approaches the acoustic relaxation time of ≈ 50 ps.^[54] The constant absorption-corrected value of $\approx 4 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in water corresponds to an incident efficiency of $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$. Reported incident efficiencies of $\approx 0.9 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ at 1 ns^[15] suggest that this plateau extends to at least 1 ns.

The convergence of ablation efficiency in air and water with increasing pulse duration is also evident in the SEM images in Figures 3b and 3c. At 10 ps, ablation in air produces a rough crater, whereas in water a smooth crater is formed. At 50 ps, the crater in air reveals a smooth central disk resembling the crater formed in water (Figure 3c). A focused-ion-beam cut (Figure 3d) reveals that this disk is slightly elevated above the surface. At 5 J cm^{-2} , almost the entire ablation crater appears smooth (Figure 3e).

Complementary PPM at a pulse duration of 50 ps (Figure 3f) reveals an inward-curved interference fringe in both air and water between 1 ns and 4 ns. This contrasts with the outward-propagating Newton rings observed during spallation in Figure 2 and indicates that the ablated material reverses direction and redeposits on the surface. The velocity of the downward-moving layer is estimated as 130 m s^{-1} , assuming a refractive index of 1 between the surface and the material layer. This assumption is supported by molecular-dynamics simulations, which predict that water does not penetrate the cavity between the spallation layer and the surface.^[11,44] In the final state, PPM reveals a bright central disk with increased reflectance in both air and water (Figure 3f, “Disk”). In air, the disk appears after $\approx 10 \text{ ns}$ and persists into the final state, closely matching the smooth central disk observed in SEM (Figure 3c). A full description of the ablation dynamics at 10 ps and 50 ps, up to delay times of $100 \mu\text{s}$, is given in Section S8 of the Supporting Information.

Figure 3. Influence of the pulse duration on the absorption-corrected volumetric ablation efficiency and the ablation morphology of Au in the phase explosion regime as well as pump-probe microscopy measurements of Au at a pulse duration of 50 ps in air and water. **a** Absorption-corrected ablation efficiency η_{abs} as a function of pulse duration τ_p for ablation in air (red squares) and water (blue circles) for $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 3 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$. The axis on the right shows the absorption-corrected specific energy for ablation ζ_{abs} . Red and blue solid lines serve as visual guides for ablation in air and water, respectively. **b** Scanning electron microscopy images of the surface morphology in air (left, red frame) and water (right, blue frame) at $\tau_p = 10 \text{ ps}$ and $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 3 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$. **c** Same as **b**, but for $\tau_p = 50 \text{ ps}$. **d** Focused ion beam cross section along the red dashed line in **c**. **e** SEM images for $\tau_p = 50 \text{ ps}$ and $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 5 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$ in air (left, red frame) and water (right, blue frame). **f** Color-coded spatiotemporal relative reflectance change $\Delta R/R_0$ for ablation in air (top) and water (bottom) at $\tau_p = 10 \text{ ps}$ and $\Phi_{\text{abs}} = 3 \text{ J cm}^{-2}$. The final state reflectance at $\Delta t = 10 \text{ s}$ is shown in a separate panel on the right ($\Delta t = 10 \text{ s}$). Redeposition is labeled as RD.

The decrease of ablation efficiency with increasing pulse duration in air (Figure 3a) can be attributed to the attenuation of stress confinement.^[27,29,75] The maximum tensile stress decreases to approximately 50% of its stress-confined value as the pulse duration approaches

the acoustic relaxation time.^[29] As a result, the tensile stress no longer exceeds the spall strength, cancelling the contribution of spallation.^[27,29]

In contrast, LAL shows nearly constant efficiency with increasing pulse duration (Figure 3a). If spallation contributed significantly to ablation in liquid, a similar decrease to that observed in air would be expected. The absence of this decrease suggests that spallation does not contribute to material removal in LAL, since the spallation layer redeposits onto the surface. This interpretation is supported by the ablation morphology (Figure 3b). In air, spallation of Au produces nano-spikes,^[93] originating from liquid bridges that solidify after tear-off of the spallation layer.^[94] Their absence in LAL points to a redeposition of the spallation layer. This conclusion is consistent with both hydrodynamic^[43,45] and molecular-dynamics simulations,^[11] the latter predicting that about 80% of the ablated material is redeposited. This value closely matches the 75% reduction in ablation efficiency observed experimentally in the phase-explosion regime (Figures 1b and 3a).

For a pulse duration of 50 ps, the ablation efficiency (Figure 3a), morphology (Figure 3c), and dynamics (Figure 3f) are similar in air and water, suggesting that ablation is governed by similar mechanisms in both environments. The inward-curved Newton rings labeled “RD” in Figure 3f already indicate redeposition in both media. In air, the observed disk (Figure 3e) resembles the pristine surface, suggesting that no material was removed in this region, consistent with redeposition. Such behavior is well established, for example in double-pulse ablation experiments where interaction of successive pulses with the ablated material leads to material redeposition.^[95-97] By analogy, the smooth surface observed in water is likewise attributed to redeposition.

In summary, the constant ablation efficiency in water, the absence of nano-spikes in LAL, and the convergence of ablation efficiency, morphology, and dynamics in air and water at long pulse durations all point to redeposition as the key mechanism limiting ablation efficiency in the phase-explosion regime in water.

2.4. Ablation efficiency under multi-pulse irradiation

To replicate conditions where multiple pulses per position are required for nanoparticle generation,^[98] ablation efficiency was evaluated by applying multiple pulses to the same position. The same pulse duration of 3 ps as in Sections 2.1 and 2.2 was used here for comparison. A temporal inter-pulse spacing of 10 s was chosen to exclude shielding by cavitation bubbles and persistent microbubbles, which have dispersed on this timescale (see $\Delta t = 10$ s Figure 2a for FeNi and Figure 3f for Au). However, nanoparticles generated during

ablation remain at the surface and contribute to shielding.^[61] This configuration resembles scalability-oriented flow setups, which suppress bubble shielding but still suffer from nanoparticle shielding.^[61,63] Incident fluence and efficiency were used to enable comparison with scalability-oriented studies, as absorption at the target surface cannot be determined in the presence of nanoparticle shielding. For Au, a fluence of 3.8 J cm^{-2} was used, corresponding to the efficiency maximum (Figure 1b). For FeNi, 12.7 J cm^{-2} was chosen as the lowest fluence yielding measurable crater volumes under multi-pulse ablation in water (Supporting Information, Section S9).

For Au, the incident ablation efficiency increases with pulse number N in both air and water, saturating at $\approx 4 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in air and $\approx 2 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in water after 5 pulses (Figure 4). Accordingly, the efficiency ratio between air and water decreases from a factor of ≈ 4 for a single pulse (see also Figure 1b) to ≈ 2 after 10 pulses.

Figure 4. Per-pulse incident ablation efficiency η_I as a function of pulse number N for Au (top) and FeNi (bottom) with a pulse duration of 3 ps at respective incident peak fluences of $\Phi_I = 3.8 \text{ J/cm}^2$ and $\Phi_I = 12.7 \text{ J/cm}^2$. The axis on the right shows the incident specific energy for ablation ζ_I .

For FeNi, the incident ablation efficiency increases steadily with pulse number in both air and water. In water, the efficiency becomes positive starting with the third pulse, as the crater center volume exceeds that of the surrounding porous area. The efficiency reaches $\approx 1.2 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in air and $\approx 0.75 \mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$ in water after 10 pulses. The efficiency ratio between air and water thus decreases to ≈ 1.6 , consistent with the trend observed for Au.

The reduced efficiency gap with increasing pulse number indicates stronger incubation in water than in air, as already observed for Ni, Fe, and W.^[73] Incubation effects are explained by two mechanisms: increased absorption due to multiple scattering at rough surfaces, and threshold reduction through defect accumulation.^[72] Because craters in water are comparatively smooth (Figure 1a), increased absorption from surface roughness plays a minor role in water, pointing to defect accumulation as the relevant mechanism. Molecular dynamics simulations show that ablation in liquid generates larger and more numerous subsurface voids than in air, due to redeposition.^[44] These defects likely enhance incubation for subsequent pulses, explaining why incubation is stronger in water than in air.

2.5. Comparison of specific ablation energy with simulations and record efficiencies

Our results are compared to molecular dynamics predictions and record LAL efficiencies in terms of the specific energy of ablation ζ , expressed in J mm^{-3} (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of ablation efficiencies for FeNi and Au from molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, experimental LAL studies, and the present work. For each entry, the laser processing approach and pulse duration τ_P are given, along with the incident pulse energy E_P . Ablation efficiencies are reported based on the incident pulse energy η_I in units of $\mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$. The incident energy for ablation ζ is calculated from the respective ablation efficiencies.

Material	Reference	Approach	τ_P	E_P	η_I	ζ_I
			[ps]	[μJ]	[$\mu\text{m}^3 \mu\text{J}^{-1}$]	[J mm^{-3}]
Fe _{0.5} Ni _{0.5}	Chen et al. ^[11]	MD simulation	10	-	0.16	6250
	Khairani et al. ^[64]	11-beam processing	10	22.5	0.23	4348
	This work	10 pulses	3	50	0.76	1316
Au	Khairani et al. ^[64]	11-beam processing	10	22.5	0.14	7143
	Kohsakowski et al. ^[66]	Wire-target in liquid jet	$\approx 10^3$	6500	0.25	4000
	Kohsakowski et al. ^[99]	Galvanometer scanner	$6 \cdot 10^3$	24300	0.26	3846
	Waag et al. ^[63]	Polygon scanner	3	90	0.30	3333
	Dittrich et al. ^[15]	Galvanometer scanner	10^3	130	0.9	1111
	This work	Single-pulse	3	25	1.08	926
	This work	10 pulses	3	15	2.32	431

Efficiencies in the scalability-oriented LAL literature are typically reported with respect to the incident pulse energy, which we also adopt here. A comparison with absorption-corrected

efficiencies is provided in Section S10 of the Supporting Information. Reported values for FeNi are around 4300 J mm^{-3} ,^[64] whereas the present multi-pulse measurement yields 1316 J mm^{-3} for 10 pulses, substantially lower than previously achieved. Molecular dynamics simulations predict even higher values of about 6250 J mm^{-3} .^[11]

Reported specific energies for ablation of Au typically are in the range of 3300 J mm^{-3} to 7100 J mm^{-3} .^[63,64,66,99] In comparison, the present study achieves 926 J mm^{-3} under single-pulse conditions and 431 J mm^{-3} for 10 pulses, nearly an order of magnitude more efficient than the best ultrafast LAL values reported to date. A notable exception is nanosecond ablation,^[15] where efficiencies of about 1100 J mm^{-3} have been demonstrated at a more favorable pulse duration that avoids nonlinear interaction with the liquid and bubble shielding.^[16] Nonetheless, the present results still show about a two-fold improvement under less favorable ultrafast conditions.

Together, these comparisons establish a clear picture of LAL efficiency. The absorption-corrected single-pulse value for Au defines a physical lower bound of only 200 J mm^{-3} , far below predictions from simulations and earlier experiments. On the incident-energy basis relevant for scalable nanoparticle production, our multi-pulse measurements for both FeNi and Au outperform all reported ultrafast LAL efficiencies, and for Au even exceed the most favorable nanosecond studies by a factor of two. The remaining gap between this physical benchmark and values achieved in practice is expected to be largely due to remaining nonlinear absorption and shielding effects. Approaches such as GHz burst processing^[100] and multi-beam processing^[64] hold promise to mitigate these losses, offering a pathway to translate the physical efficiency limits demonstrated here into scalable, high-throughput nanoparticle generation.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, the suppression of laser ablation efficiency in water has been quantified through a direct comparison with air at the same absorbed peak fluence, revealing an increase in absorption-corrected specific energy for ablation by a factor of four from 50 J mm^{-3} to 200 J mm^{-3} . Material redeposition, induced by liquid confinement, was identified as the dominant cause of this increase, thereby experimentally validating simulation predictions. This conclusion is supported by multiple independent observations: (i) negligible influence of acoustic transmission losses, (ii) negligible thermal conduction losses, (iii) direct observation of spallation-layer redeposition in FeNi, (iv) convergence of LAL efficiency with increasing pulse duration, (v) absence of nano-spikes in LAL compared to air, (vi) formation of

redeposition disks in both air and water, (vii) inward-bound Newton rings, and (viii) stronger incubation in water than in air.

The maximum specific energy for ablation in water determined here is 431 J mm^{-3} under multi-pulse incident conditions, nearly an order of magnitude lower than the best values reported for ultrafast LAL. These findings establish the practical potential of LAL, underscoring its promise for green, energy-efficient, and high-throughput nanoparticle synthesis.

5. Experimental Section

5.1. Target preparation and characterization

Polycrystalline Au and $\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}$ targets, each 1 mm thick, were embedded in epoxy resin, sanded, and polished to achieve a root mean square surface roughness of approximately 20 nm for Au and 5 nm for FeNi. Au polishing followed Reference^[54] and FeNi Reference^[75]. Optical and thermophysical properties of the samples are provided in the Supporting Information Sections S7 and S1, respectively. Ablation morphology was measured using SEM (TESCAN, LRYA3). The ablation volume V_{abl} was determined using confocal microscopy (Leitz Ergoplan, 50x/0.85) with a lateral resolution of 500 nm and an axial resolution of 1 nm and averaged over ten individual ablation craters for each set of parameters (see Supporting Information, Section S11). The ablation efficiency was defined as $\eta = V_{\text{abl}} E^{-1}$.^[101] Here E denotes either the absorbed pulse energy E_{abs} , yielding the absorption-corrected ablation efficiency η_{abs} , or the incident pulse energy E_{I} , yielding the incident ablation efficiency η_{I} .

5.2. Pump-probe microscopy

PPM measurements were performed using the setup shown in **Figure 5a**. A femtosecond laser (Spectra-Physics, Spirit 16W HE) emitting pulses at a repetition rate of 500 Hz, a wavelength of 1040 nm, a pulse duration of 500 fs and a pulse energy of $E_{\text{P}} = 120 \mu\text{J}$ (pulse-to-pulse fluctuations $< 1\%$), was used. The pre-pulse and post-pulse contrast ratios of the laser source were $E_{\text{P}}/E_{\text{pre}} = 1019$ and $E_{\text{P}}/E_{\text{post}} = 713$, respectively. Here, E_{pre} is the pulse energy of the pre-pulse, and E_{post} is the energy of the post-pulse. The pulses were split into a pump pulse (red) and probe pulse (green) at a 9:1 energy ratio using a half-wave plate (HWP) and a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) combination. Another HWP-PBS combination regulated the pump pulse energy.

Single pump pulses were selected by a mechanical shutter (MS). The pump pulse duration was continuously adjustable between 500 fs and 90 ps (FWHM, measured via intensity

autocorrelation with sech^2 temporal pulse shape) using a pulse stretcher. A plano-convex lens (L) with a 100 mm focal length focused the p-polarized pump pulses onto the target.

For ablation in air, the targets were placed in the focus and irradiated at an incidence angle of $\theta = 35^\circ$. For LAL, the targets were placed in a quartz glass cuvette, submerged under 4 mm deionized water, and enclosed by a 1 mm fused silica slide (Corning 7980). The incidence angle for LAL was $\theta = 25.6^\circ$ due to refraction at the air-glass and glass-water interfaces.

The beam caustic was measured with a focal beam profiler (MicroSpotMonitor, Primes GmbH) (see Supporting Information, Section S12), yielding $M^2 \approx 1.2$ and a beam waist radius of $(15 \pm 1) \mu\text{m}$. The peak fluence was then calculated as $\Phi_0 = 2 \cdot E_P \cdot \pi^{-1} \cdot w_0^{-2}$. Notably, Φ_0 represents the peak fluence, which is a factor of two higher than the average fluence.^[102]

Figure 5. PPM and self-reflection measurements setups. **a** Pump-probe microscopy setup with pump-branch in red and probe-branch in green. **b** Pump-probe image post-processing demonstrated at example images recorded by irradiation Au with a pulse duration of 3 ps in air. **c** Photodiode calibration. **d** Self-reflection measurement in air. **e** Transmittance measurement in water. **f** Self-reflection measurement in water. The following components are depicted: Half-wave plate (HWP), polarizing beam splitter (PBS), second harmonic generation module (SHG), beam dump (BD), mechanical shutter (MS), mirror (M), plano-convex lens (L), tube lens (TL), quarter-wave plate (QWP) and band-pass filter (BPF).

The probe pulse was frequency doubled to 520 nm and used for a time delayed, collimated illumination of the ablation process. An optical delay line introduced a variable time delay ($\Delta t \leq 4$ ns) between the pump and probe pulses. For $\Delta t > 4$ ns, a second electronically delayed laser (wavelength: 532 nm, pulse duration: 500 ps, pulse energy: 40 μ J) served as the probe pulse source.

The target surface was imaged with a 50x, $NA = 0.42$ objective (Mitutoyo, M Plan Apo SL) onto a CMOS camera (PCO AG, pco.pixelfly usb). A bandpass filter (BPF, 520 ± 10 nm) in front of the camera suppressed scattered pump radiation and ambient light. The delay time zero ($\Delta t = 0$ ns) was defined as the temporal overlap of the pump and probe pulse peaks and determined with an accuracy of approximately 500 fs by the instantaneous reflectance increase of Si irradiated below its melting threshold fluence.^[54]

For each desired Δt , the target was moved to a pristine position, and two images were recorded: $C_0(\Delta t = -1$ s) (reference) and $C(\Delta t)$. The relative reflectance change was then calculated pixel-wise using the expression: $\Delta R/R_0 = (C(\Delta t) - C_0)/C_0$ (Figure 5b).

5.3. Self-reflectance measurement

Self-reflectance R_S , was measured with a photodiode (PD) (Hamamatsu Photonics, S1336-8BQ) and current integrator (Wieserlabs GmbH, WL-IPD4A). The PD was calibrated as shown in Figure 5c. A 100 mm plano-convex lens focused the pump pulses onto the PD, with a neutral density filter (NDF) in front of the PD ensured linear operation. The time-integrated photocurrent q_0 was proportional to the incident pulse energy E_0 . For measurements in air, the target was introduced into the setup, and the charge q_A , induced by the reflected pump pulse, was recorded (Figure 5d). R_S at the air-target interface was then calculated as: $R_S = q_A/q_0$. For self-reflectance measurements in water, the transmittance through an 8 mm water-filled cuvette was determined by measuring the charge q_T (Figure 5e). The total transmittance is $T_{tot} = q_T/q_0 = (1-R_G)^2 \cdot (1-R_W)^2 \cdot T_4^2$, where R_G is the reflectance at the air-glass interface, R_W is the reflectance at the glass-water interface, and T_4 is the transmittance through a 4 mm water layer. Following this, the self-reflectance at the water-target interface was determined by measuring the charge q_W using the setup in Figure 5f. Here the total reflectance is $R_{tot} = (1-R_G)^2 \cdot (1-R_W)^2 \cdot T_4^2 \cdot R_S$. By comparing T_{tot} and R_{tot} , the self-reflectance at the water-target interface was obtained as: $R_S = T_{tot}/R_{tot}$. The transmittance to the target surface immersed in water is $T = T_{tot}^{1/2}$. The absorbed peak fluence was calculated as $\Phi_{abs} = (1 - R_S) \cdot T \cdot \Phi_0$, where Φ_0 denotes the irradiated peak fluence. The incident peak fluence was calculated as $\Phi_I = T \cdot \Phi_0$. T is provided in Section S13 of the Supporting Information and R_S in Section S7. Below the

respective optical breakdown and ablation thresholds, T and R_s were validated against literature values, showing agreement within 2%.

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Author contribution statement

M.S., A.P., C.E., K.E., O.K. and C.B. conducted the experiments and analyzed the data. M.S. and H.P.H. interpreted the data. D.R. conducted the two-temperature model calculations. M.S. and H.P.H. wrote the manuscript, and all authors contributed to its improvement. B.G., S.B., and H.P.H. supervised the project.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525417>, reference number 15525417.

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Table of contents:

Laser ablation in liquid enables nanoparticle synthesis from diverse materials but remains less energy-efficient than ablation in air. This study quantifies the absorption-corrected ablation efficiency and experimentally confirms redeposition as the key loss mechanism using pump-probe microscopy. The determined efficiency limit offers a benchmark for modeling and highlights the optimization potential of laser-based nanoparticle production.

